

Modifications of Consonants in Connected speech.

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Annotation

This article focuses on Modifications of Consonants in Connected speeches are changing in meaning as contemporary English undergoes change. Consonants in English can function as a predicate.

Keywords: Modification, alveolar, allophonic, nasal, complete, incomplete, plosion, assimilation, consonants, voiced, voiceless, combination

Аннотация

В этой статье основное внимание уделяется модификациям согласных в связных речах, которые меняются по значению по мере того, как современный английский язык претерпевает изменения. Согласные в английском языке могут выполнять функцию сказуемого.

Ключевые слова: Модификация, альвеолярная, аллофоническая, носовая, полная, неполная, пlosion, ассимиляция, согласные, звонкие, глухие, сочетания

Allophonic variations of speech sounds brought about by a word's placement are known as sound modifications. Typically, they are fairly consistent and can be expressed as guidelines that foretell the usage of specific allophones in every role. Changes in sound can be heard both between words as well as at word borders. There are various kinds of sound editing which describe either vowels, consonants, or both in modern English.

Consonants are characterized by the following types of sound modifications: assimilation, accommodation, elision, and inserting.

Assimilation is the adaptive modification of a consonant by a neighbouring consonant within a speech chain. There are different types of assimilation.

1) Assimilation affecting the place of articulation includes the following modifications of consonant

— alveolar [t, d, n, l, s, z] become dental before interdental [ð, θ] (eighth, breadth, on the, all the, guess that, does that);

— alveolar [t, d] become post-alveolar before post-alveolar [r] (true, dream);

— alveolar [s, z] become post-alveolar before apical forelingual [ʃ] (this shelf, does she);

— alveolar [t, d] become fricative before palatal mediolingual [j] (graduate,

congratulate);

— nasal [m, n] become labio-dental before labio-dental [f, fort]

— nasal [n] becomes dental before interdental [θ] (seventh);

— nasal [n] becomes velar before backlingual [k] (think);

— nasal [n] becomes palato-alveolar before palato-alveolar [tʃ, dʒ] (pinch, change).

2) Assimilation affecting the manner of articulation includes the following modifications of consonants:

— loss of plosion in the sequence of two stops [p, t, k, b, d, g] (and dad, that tape, fact) or in the sequence of a stop and an affricate (a pointed chin, a sad joke);

— nasal plosion in the combination of a plosive consonant and a nasal sonorant (sudden, happen, at night, submarine, let me);

— lateral plosion in the sequence of an occlusive consonant and a lateral sonorant (settle, please, apple);

— anticipating lip-rounded position in the combination of consonants [t, d, k, g, s] and a sonorant [w] (quite, swim, dweller).

3) Assimilation affecting the work of the vocal cords includes the following modifications of consonants:

— progressive partial devoicing of the sonorous [m, n, l, w, r, j] before voiceless [s, p, t, k, f, θ, ʃ] (small, slow, place, fly, sneer, try, throw, square, twilight, pure, few, tune, at last, at rest);

— progressive voicing or devoicing of the contracted forms of the auxiliary verbs is, has depending on the preceding phoneme (That's right. Jack's gone. John's come.);

— progressive voicing or devoicing of the possessive suffixes -'s / -s', the plural suffix -(e)s of nouns or the third person singular ending -(e)s of verbs according to the phonetic context (Jack's, Tom's, Mary's, George's; girls, boys, dishes, maps; reads, writes, watches);

— progressive voicing or devoicing of the suffix -ed depending on the preceding sound (lived, played, worked);

— regressive voicing or devoicing in compound words (gooseberry,)

It's important to mention that English consonants are not subjected to voiced-voiceless or voiceless-voiced assimilation within non-compound words (anecdote, birthday, obstinate) or in free combinations of two notional words (sit down, this book, these socks, white dress).

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